

THE ROLE OF INTERNET TECHNOLOGY IN THE MODERN CONCEPT OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Jumakulova Khalima Alisherovna

Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy
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ABSTRACT

The use of information and communication technologies (ICT) can significantly expand educational opportunities. Standard forms of teaching are becoming less and less likely to attract the interest of students; there is a need to look for new methods, one of which should be the active use of digital resources in the classroom. This article examines technologies for teaching writing in English using ICT.

In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in lessons in educational institutions has been increasingly raised. These are not only new technical means, but also forms, teaching methods, and a new approach to the learning process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is the formation and development of the communicative culture of students, training in practical mastery of a foreign language. Modern pedagogical technologies such as collaborative learning, project-based methods, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources help to implement a student-centered approach to learning, ensure individualization and differentiation of learning, taking into account children's abilities, their level, inclinations, etc. [1]. Thus, the goal of the work is to analyze the connection between the use of Internet resources and the quality of knowledge of high school students in English lessons.

In English lessons using the Internet, you can solve a number of didactic tasks: develop reading skills and abilities using materials from the global network; improve the writing skills of schoolchildren; replenish students' vocabulary; to form stable motivation in schoolchildren to learn English. Forms of working with Internet resources in foreign language lessons include:

- learning vocabulary;
- practicing pronunciation;
- training in dialogical and monologue speech;
- teaching writing;
- practicing grammatical phenomena.

Students can take part in tests, quizzes, competitions, olympiads held on the Internet, correspond with peers from other countries, participate in chats, video conferences, etc. They can also receive information on the problem they are working on at the moment within the project [2].

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Modern pedagogical technologies such as collaborative learning, project-based methods, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources help to implement a student-centered approach to learning, ensure individualization and differentiation of learning, taking into account children's abilities, their level, inclinations, etc. [3]. Thus, the goal of the work is to analyze the connection between the use of Internet resources and the quality of knowledge of high school students in English lessons. The possibilities for using Internet resources are enormous. The global Internet creates conditions for obtaining any information students and teachers need, located anywhere in the world: regional studies material, news from the lives of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, necessary literature, etc.

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- practicing grammatical phenomena [4].

Mastering communicative and intercultural competence is impossible without communication practice and the use of Internet resources in a foreign language lesson. The virtual environment of the Internet allows one to go beyond time and space boundaries, providing its users with the opportunity for authentic communication with real interlocutors on topics that are relevant to both parties [5].

However, we must not forget that the Internet is only an auxiliary technical means of teaching, and in order to achieve optimal results it is necessary to correctly integrate its use into the lesson process.

After analyzing the educational sites that the Internet offers schoolchildren, we selected those that we will use in our research activities. Interesting further information on a variety of topics can be found on the BBC website (<http://www.bbc.co.uk>). The site offers interesting information on the topics: "Nature", "Flora and fauna of planet Earth", "Prehistoric times", "The work of the human brain", "Organs of the human body", "Space" [6]. In addition, during the learning process, students may be offered tests in English that will help them evaluate their lifestyle, intelligence, memory and attention.

The English 101 Grammar website (<http://lessons.englishgrammar101.com>) will help you prepare for grammar lessons. For each rule, a series of training exercises is proposed. When working with computer technologies, the role of the teacher also changes, whose task is to support and guide the development of students' personalities and their creative search.

Relations with students are built on the principles of cooperation and joint creativity. In these conditions, a revision of the organizational forms of educational work that have developed today is inevitable: an increase in independent individual and group work of students, a departure from traditional classes with a predominance of the explanatory and illustrative teaching method, an increase in the volume of practical and creative work of a search and research nature. In this type of cooperation between the Internet and classes, a project form of educational activity is often used.

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